

THE STORY "KARAKOZ MAJNOON" BY SAID AHMED

Abdurahmonova Mavluda Ibragimovna

Academic Lyceum of Termiz State University

Teacher of Native Language and Literature

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Abstract: In this article, information about the life and work of our famous writer Said Ahmed is presented, in the story "Karakoz Majnun", which is one of the rare works of the writer, the character of a faithful animal is shown through the image of a dog.

Keywords: writer, faithful, image, symbol, story, picture

Introduction: In this play, the original base of national art and epoch of a literary history are revealed. The content of this play can also be widely developed in the opinion parallels of folk traditions, national customs, and characteristics of Soviet mentality. This play is specifically about the sense of devotion and eternal love. According to the words of the poet Saadi: "I could easily be your friend, not share the fortune theme, but since true love, I chose to love you", or according to the words of the great Öthman: "Standard of a sick person is that she wants to be treated quickly. The standard of a Rikthe (an obsessed person) is that she does not want to be treated at all."

The modern stage art of independent Uzbekistan is daringly striving to solve the national problems in the drama. We can judge this by the fact that some theater plays by contemporary writers are connected with the wet history of the people of Uzbekistan. The play "Karakoz Majnoon" by Said Ahmed shows the uniqueness of ethnic creativity. The main idea of the play is based on the legends of people and themes of oriental love which are typical for the consciousness at that time.

An interesting trend in Uzbek drama is the theme of schizophrenia and especially the theme of the generation gap between parents and children. In a number of stories and plays, the literary and artistic achievements are being connected with modern problems. Young Uzbek writers have turned to the theme of the border between dream and reality because the opposition of East and West is realized as a result of a collision of the opposite characters presented by life. This creates a situation not only of the personal, but also a social, national and universal interest.

Background of the Author

Professor Said Ahmed is a prominent Uzbek writer, a specialist in Uzbek literature and folklore, and the writer of numerous critical articles. As a scientist,

S. Ahmed is already widely known. His monograph on the Uzbek National Hero Korodin, published a year ago, has testified to this. Said Ahmed has acquired his fame as a writer not so long ago. His new collection of short stories, "The Life on the Banks of the Amu-Darya," is the writer's second book. His first book of short stories was published under the unassuming title "Short Stories" in 1947. The contemporary Uzbek literature developed in new forms and directions. In particular, the vital problems of modern life were being comprehensively discussed in literary works. S. Ahmed belongs to this trend of contemporary literature. He portrayed life as he saw it. His short stories are the sincere interpretation of the life of the Uzbek people. "The Short Stories of S. Ahmed" was received in a friendly way by our readers.

Said Ahmed originally worked in "Mushtum" magazine, radio board of trustees of Uzbekistan (1942-1943), presently "Voice of Uzbekistan" paper (1942-1947), "Sharq tyzni" magazine (1948-1950). His most memorable story assortment "Tortiq" was distributed in 1940. During the conflict and after the conflict, Said Ahmed composed numerous feuilletons, papers and stories. His assortments, for example, "emergency room yurak" (1942), "Fergana stories" (1948), "Love" (1949) were distributed. In his accounts, for example, "Fortune", "Shout", "Thank you, my dears", he excitingly depicts the awful outcomes of WWII, praises the legends of the conflict.

The author's accounts encapsulate Oibek's ability of mental symbolism, Gafur Ghulam's humor, and the compactness of Abdulla Qahhor's portrayal. He endeavors to draw a philosophical speculation from every occasion he portrays in his accounts, to communicate the occasions with expressive effect, to accomplish various imaginative pictures. Various works, for example, "Desert Bird", "Orik Domla", "Hawk", "Man and Wolf", "Boston", "Toyboshi" were new in crafted by Said Ahmed and in Uzbek writing.

The heroes of Author's accounts are our counterparts whose internal world is rich. The essayist made life characters in progress "The Legend of the Mountain", "Emerald", "Birth of Adoration", "There was fire in your eyes", "Race", "Alla", "Lights of Iqbal". In his comic stories, Said Ahmed snickers at the malevolent traditions that are an obstruction to our advancement, and raises significant profound issues. Many his comics, for example, "Khanka and Tanka" and "Lampa Shisha" are confirmation of our perspective.

Said Ahmad established the theater of miniatures on Uzbek radio and TV with his little comic works.

Author bit by bit moved from stories to making huge materials. In the set of three "Ufq" (1949), which he made after the brief tales "Karddon Dalalar" and "Hukm" (1958), distributed in 1964, he examines the issues of the pre-and post-war period. The book "Quietness" (1988) uncovered the wrongs of the stagnation time frame. As of late, he has worked in Oybek, G'. He composed journals about Ghulam, A. Qakhor, M. Shaikhzada, Shuhrat, Mirtemir and S. Zunnunova.

Saeed Ahmed is otherwise called a writer. He is the creator of stage works, for example, "Ladies' Revolt", "The Spouse".

Saeed Ahmed is likewise a craftsman who was exposed to a rush of suppression in the last part of the 50s and endured jail sentences. He is blamed for being a "individual from the counter Soviet patriot bunch, propagator of hurtful thoughts" and is detained in Jezkazgan camp, Karaganda district of Kazakhstan. His assortment of brief tales "Karakoz Majnoon" (2002) communicates the unpleasant truth about this.

A progression of brief tales and stories remembered for the assortment of the essayist "I lost and found", three-volume "Sailanma", "Karakoz Majnun", "Kiprikdagi tong" vouch for his happy innovativeness during the long periods of freedom. A considerable lot of the essayist's works have been converted into related and unknown dialects.

Individuals' essayist of Uzbekistan Said Ahmed is the champ of various state grants. Specifically, during the long stretches of autonomy, he was granted the "Dostlik" and "For Incredible Administrations" orders. He was likewise granted the title of "Legend of Uzbekistan".

The story story is not very complicated. An aging Saadat Aya has been away for several decades, marrying on those sides and waiting for her child son, Borikhon. He remembers her in the morning prayer on the day of God's giving. The nature of Saadat aya embodies the contemplation of both this world and this world, typical of the true Muslim grandmothers of Uzbekistan. The old woman mulzam, who heard the news of her son from her granddaughter Anwar, becomes. Author describes this change in the old woman: "erraim, who does not give a word to someone, has broken the old woman's horn, and muqim sat in the house without a threshold". One day, Saadat Aya sets out with her dog Karakoz towards her daughter's House. Focus on their process of going and coming. Along the way, Adib said that every movement of the dog, its slings, its jump, its eating like a wind, its cheerfulness, let's say, " one ear is sharpened and one is

scapegoat and masculinity", skillfully describing situations such as "tirelessly chasing "cats encountered on the road," irking at birds in trees". The old woman honors her dog as a member of her house.

Conclusion

In place of the conclusion, it should be said that a huge amount of meaning is concentrated in the story. Uzbek traditions are emphasized by showing the deeds of an unworthy child. Or rather, the fact that the death of a dog stands on a high spiritual career in relation to the destruction of the mother's heart by a son is all the time glorious.

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